

Exploring Subhash Chandra's Morals and Ideals through the Play 'Subhashbhasam'.

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ABSTRACT

Shantinath Ghosh's play 'Subhashbhasam' is a social modern Sanskrit drama based on the life and leadership story of Subhas Chandra Bose. The play is divided into seven scenes and it delves into Subhash Chandra's thoughts, ideals and important aspects of the freedom movement. The playwright's simple and straightforward language creates lively dialogues between the characters, which bring the drama to life. Subhash Chandra's morality, determination and patriotism shine through in every scene. The use of music in the play enhances the emotional depth, which leaves a deep impression on the audience. The artistes of 'Surbharti Cultural Institute' have performed the play on various stages, which serves as an inspiration for the present generation. The play is not just a piece of art, but a powerful message written to evoke the spirit of patriotism and contribution of Subhash Chandra in the history of freedom struggle. It reminds us that freedom can be achieved through struggle and self-sacrifice, which is very relevant for today's generation. In short, the play 'Subhashbhasam' is based on a historical story, but it is also a source of inspiration for the modern audience. The various elements and story presentation of the play highlight Subhash Chandra's qualities of self-sacrifice and bravery, which are an integral part of our independence history.

Introduction:

Shantinath Ghosh's drama 'Subhasbhasam' is an important historical and social drama, which is written on the life and ideals of eminent revolutionary Subhas Chandra Bose. The drama is not only a depiction of Subhash Chandra's personal life, but also depicts an important chapter in our national history. In his writings, the playwright reveals the depth of Subhash Chandra's self-sacrifice, leadership and political thought, which played an important role in the development of Indian national consciousness at that time. The play brings out the importance of Subhash Chandra's thoughts and actions in the context of contemporary society and history. Subhash Chandra Bose's liberation war ideas, his powerful speeches and political initiatives come alive in every scene of the play. The dramatist beautifully presented the political context and brought before the audience the social unrest of the time, the desire for national unity and independence.

Shantinath Ghosh has reflected not only the life story of Subhash Chandra but also the various aspects of the freedom struggle and its impact through the play. He was able to portray to the audience the attitudes and thoughts of the brave fighters of that era, which are still relevant to us today. This play reminds us that achieving freedom requires not just war, but a way of thinking that unites nations. The play 'Subhasbhasam' creates awareness among the audience through a powerful political statement. The play creates a deep interest and passion for our national spirit and history, which inspires the new generation in the spirit of patriotism and struggle. This play by Shantinath Ghosh is equally relevant today and is remembered by us. How these important chapters of history guide our present and future.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

For my research progress three patriotic plays written by playwright Shantinath Ghosh are discussed as reference material. Apart from this, a lot of information has been gathered in the discussion of the plays with the playwright Shantinath Ghosh, as well as various methods of obtaining information from printed books, online, some folk practices etc. The analysis of character development and decorative vision in the said dramas is supported by the book 'Sahitya Darpan' written by Acharya Vishwanath, the book 'Dasarupak' written by Acharya Dhananjay.

Plot and Structure of Drama: 'Subhasbhasam':

The play 'Subhasbhasam' is based on the life and work of Subhas Chandra Bose, divided into seven scenes. Each scene depicts a special chapter of Subhash Chandra's life, where his ideals and struggles are

reflected. In the history of modern Sanskrit literature, all the poets who have enriched Sanskrit literature by composing poetry with their talent, one of whom is 'Subhashbhasam' written by Shantinath Ghosh. The subject of the discussion book is Subhash's intention to take monasticism, Otten Saheb's slap during his education at Presidency College (now Presidency University), the influence of Benimadhab Das, the headmaster of Ravens School during Subhash's childhood in Cuttack, Odisha, Vivekananda's thoughts on India and Subhash's impact on Subhash's life mainly in the short form of the play. Social policy, spiritual thought, disagreement with the Congress organization in the freedom movement, establishment of new organization, disappearance from home to achieve greater goals, the organization of struggle in Singapore and outside India have been briefly presented by the dramatist in the small scale of the play.

On the banks of the Ganges near the Vishwanath temple in Varanasi, tired Subhas Vishwanath prayed to Mahadev after hearing the Vandana and asked how he would attain moksha¹? Swami Brahmananda, knowing the cause of his weeping, assured Subhash that Indian Kṛṣṇa dharma required a dedicated and strong Sadhana for its own Parigraha. In the second scene, Subhash Chandra and his friends complete all the arrangements to perform the annual festival of Presidency College. The students of the Inaugural Music College performed after Mr. Otten's arrival on this occasion. Otten Saheb asked him to stop the music during the commencement ceremony, slapped Hemant when he protested and decided to rusticate Subhash from the college². Subhash was determined not to accept any scholarship offered by the British.

The third scene sees Subhash's father, Janakinath, worried about the future as Subhash is determined not to accept any scholarship despite passing the ICS exam with honours. While conversing with his wife Prabhavati and another son, Saratchandra, Mr. Taggart enters and says angrily that Subhash Chandra has joined an anti-English organization called the Bengal Volunteers. So Subhash Chandra should leave the association of that organization. In the fourth scene, it can be seen that revolutionaries such as Hemchandra, Surya Sen and others are busy discussing in the office room of Bengal Volunteers. After entering Subhash Chandra's room, Hemchandra assigned the responsibility of volunteers to him. The members of the revolutionary organization vowed that under the leadership of Subhash, they would sacrifice themselves for the freedom of the country⁴. In the fifth scene of the play, a tearful Subhash is lying on his bed under house arrest in his Elgin Road residence, expressing his grief to his mother Prabhavati about how the British are repeatedly imprisoning him without any guilt. Then Subhash

Chandra said to Shishir that the true meaning of service to the country is self-sacrifice. Then the house arrest Subhash came out in the guise of a monk with dust in the eyes of the British Police⁵.

In the sixth scene we see Rasbihari Bose at his house doing housework. Rasbihari tells his wife that all his efforts have failed. He laments to his wife and says that the freedom of the country was his only goal, which is why he tried his best to promote the freedom movement in different states of India, starting from Bangladesh, but he did not fail⁶. When the British tried to imprison him and came to Japan to defend himself with special tactics and adopted various means of India's freedom movement with the help of local administrators, all efforts failed. Finally, Subhash Chandra came to Japan and led the freedom struggle and together with the leaders of the Indian Independence Association and Azad Hind Fauj Bahini went to Delhi and created an independent government in the territory - this is the subject of the play 'Subhashbhasam' written by playwright Shantinath Ghosh⁷.

In the first scene, we see the background of Subhash's childhood and education. During this time, the seeds of patriotism begin to grow in him, which plays an important role later in life. His keen interest in education and love for his motherland is evident here. In the second and third scenes, Subhash's political activities and sense of nationalism are highlighted. How he started his struggle against the British rule and got involved in various movements is depicted here in detail. The audience can feel his leadership qualities and indomitable spirit in this scene. In the fourth and fifth scenes, Subhash's humanitarian qualities are reflected through his narration of various instances of social service and sacrifice. At this stage, his contributions to the society through his various social projects and initiatives are highlighted. Scenes six and seven show the critical moments in Subhash's life. Political pressure and struggle are discussed here. The end of the play establishes the ideal of Subhash Chandra among the audience and respect for him. The play represents not only the life of Subhash Chandra, but also a part of the entire Indian freedom movement, instilling a new sense of patriotism and nationalism in the minds of the audience.

Use of Panchasandhi according to viswanatha:

The structure of the drama is based on the structure of Panchasandhi, which ensures the dynamics and order of the drama. The story of the drama flows based on context, tension, conflict, crisis and resolution. Each scene reveals a new aspect of Subhash Chandra's thoughts and actions, which holds the audience's attention.

Dialogue and use of language:

The dialogues of the play are simple and written in the language of everyday life, which makes the idea of the play easy to understand. Through the dialogue between the characters, the dramatist shows their emotions, thoughts and experiences. These dialogues bring the drama to life and help connect with the audience.

The Role of Music in “Subhasbhasam”

The use of music in a play shows the skill of the playwright. Music helps to enhance the emotion and importance of the drama, which creates a deep feeling in the mind of the audience. At various moments in Subhas Chandra's life, the emotions of the play are enhanced through music, which instills in the audience a deep respect for Subhas Chandra's ideals.

Drama performances and reactions:

The play has been performed by the artistes of Surabharati Cultural Institute on different stages of the country. In each case there is a new awakening among the audience to Subhash Chandra's ideals and sacrifices. The success of the play depends on the skill of the dramatist and the performance of the artists. Discussions and thoughts about Subhash Chandra's thoughts and ideals have started among the audience.

Overview

This play is intended to inspire the new generation to be patriotic. The role of the play is immense in spreading the ideals of Subhash Chandra among today's youth society and creating national awareness among them. It reminds us that the life and work of a great personality like Subhash Chandra Bose is an example for us, enriching our national pride and heritage. Thus, the play 'Subhashbhasam' is not just entertainment, but a learning experience, which connects us with history and helps us to become responsible citizens. So, this play is an inspiration for us, which motivates us to follow the ideals of a great leader like Subhash Chandra.

Significance of the drama ‘Subhasavasam’

Through the drama, the importance of Subhash Chandra Bose in the history of freedom struggle becomes clear. His life and works are a source of inspiration for the next generation, which inspires them with

patriotism. The drama has heartwarming presented the story of Subhash Chandra's ideals and sacrifices and further awakened our national consciousness.

Conclusion:

The play 'Subhasbhasam' is a profound and important portrayal of the life and work of Subhas Chandra Bose. The dramatist's creative writing, characterization and musical combination have taken this play to a special position, conveying Subhash Chandra's ideals and spirit of self-sacrifice in the hearts of the audience. Through the drama we are exposed to the political struggles, social disparities and the importance of nationalism of the time. The drama is not just a work of art but it portrays an important chapter of our history. The life and philosophy of Subhash Chandra Bose helps us understand the necessity and importance of freedom struggle⁸. His story of leadership and sacrifice is not confined to the pages of history; Rather, it has been established as a symbol of our national consciousness.

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